

Vision & Mission of NCC for the Socialization of Youth

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Abstract

This abstract delves into the vision and mission of the National Cadet Corps (NCC) in India, focusing on its role in the socialization of youth. The NCC aims to develop disciplined and patriotic citizens through its comprehensive training programs. Its vision is to create a pool of motivated and responsible young individuals who contribute positively to society. The mission includes instilling values of leadership, teamwork, and civic responsibility among cadets. By engaging in various community service activities and military training, NCC fosters a sense of duty, national pride, and social cohesion. The program also emphasizes physical fitness, mental resilience, and ethical conduct. This review highlights the NCC's impact on youth development, illustrating how it prepares young people to face challenges and take on leadership roles in society. The NCC's holistic approach aims to nurture well-rounded individuals capable of making meaningful contributions to the nation.

Key words: NCC, Socialization, Youths.

Introduction

Indian Government of India has been proactive in inspiring and nurturing the youth through various initiatives across different sectors, aimed at crafting youth-centric policies and executing programs for their holistic development. These initiatives stand the National Cadet Corps (NCC), established in 1948 within the Ministry of Defence, often regarded as the nation's 2nd line of defense. Remarkably, it holds the distinction of being the largest youth organization globally. Ministry of Youth Affairs and Sports has spearheaded eleven additional impactful programs targeting youth development. NSS, inaugurated in 1969, emerges as a significant cornerstone in India's youth development landscape, focusing explicitly on nurturing the potential of young individuals. Its underlying philosophy revolves around fostering youth development. Understanding the essence of NCC and NSS, along with comparing the roles of both organizations in youth development is essential, prompting researchers to delve deeper into this subject. Former DG NCC M.C. Bhandari, AVSM & Bar, said, "The youth in our country, as all over the world, are a great resource of the nation for development, innovation and social change. Thus, there is a need to harness youth power for nation building by making them good citizens who are committed to society and nationhood. This can best be done by inculcating patriotism, providing good education, empowerment and employment".

The National Cadet Corps (NCC) stands as a leading voluntary organization for young individuals, sharing similar objectives with many such organizations worldwide. Its roots trace back to the establishment of the 'University Corps' under the Indian Defence Act of 1917, aimed at addressing Army shortages. Subsequently, in 1920, with the enactment of the Indian Territorial Act, the 'University Corps' evolved into the University Training Corps (UTC), later renamed the University Officers Training Corps (UOTC) in 1942. Recognizing the necessity for a national-level youth organization to prepare young boys and girls as future leaders across various spheres, including the

defense forces, our leaders took action. A committee chaired by HN Kunzru was established in 1946 to fulfill this vision under the direction of our 1st PM, Pandit Jawaharlal Nehru.

As a result, the National Cadet Corps was formally established on July 16th, 1948, through the NCC Act, XXXI of 1948, Ministry of Defence. Today, it boasts an enrolled strength of 1,700,000 cadets across India. The NCC operates an extensive National Building Program aimed at nurturing the development of young boys and girls nationwide. Amrita Nayak Dutta (2024) forwarded through 'The Indian Express' that the Ministry of Defence is planning a phase-wise augmentation of the National Cadet Corps (NCC) from the current 17 lakh cadets to 27 lakh in the next 10 years. This is aimed at enhancing the reach of the tri-service organization to a greater number of educational institutions, with a focus on border areas. The Ministry has previously said that an increasing demand for NCC throughout the country to open this in the schools and colleges on a voluntary basis. The NCC, grooms and trains youth in social services, discipline, adventure activities and given basic military training, though there's no liability to take part in active military service after the course. However, NCC organization has planned to include it to elective subject at college level and the overall revision of syllabus in line with the NEP-2020 is also being worked out and there are plans to include NCC as an elective subject in the curriculum of colleges.

Objectives:

The study about NCC structure in the institutions is interesting because of NCC is carrying youth for their carrier building and initiated them to serve for nation as a social worker or social activist in society. Now a day, we can see that our Prime Minister Shri Narendra Modi ji was also a NCC Cadet. All social workers have volunteer social service organization as NCC and NSS etc., in their motivation for social services. The objectives decided to study of Vision & Mission of NCC for the Socialization of Youth are given below:-

1. To know the concept of National Cadet Corps in India.
2. To explore the role of NCC in social services and community development in the society.
3. To analyze NCC practices for Socialization of Youth in India.

Socialization of Youth

Government of India has taken an initiative to develop policies for motivation of youth and to design and implement programs for youth development. NCC is big and an ideal organization formed by Government of India to initialized social service activities through basic military training under the Ministry of Defence. It is an organization of youngsters in India and all over the world to serve country and socialization of society. Government of India has lot of programs for the development of youngsters and out of those are National Youth Policy, National Service Scheme (NSS), Nehru Yuva Kendra Sangathan, Rovers & Rangers, Rajiv Gandhi National Institute of Youth Development, National Youth Corps, Scouting and Guiding Scheme and International Cooperation for youth etc. NSS is parallel organization in institutions was established in 1969 for initiate the enthusiasm and to socialization in the youngsters. The concept of the scheme is the development and socialization of youth. So that no doubt the NCC is the process and practice of socialization and patriotic youth over the country and the world.

(a) Aims and Motto of NCC

Initially, NCC training primarily focused on military-oriented activities, with limited emphasis on adventure and sports. However, over time, the objectives have evolved, including:

- To Develop Character Comradeship, discipline, leadership, secular outlook, spirit adventure and the ideals of selfless service amongst youth of the country.
- To create human resource of organized, trend and motivated youth, to provide leadership in all walks of life and always available for the service of the nation.
- To provide suitable environment to motivate the youth to take up a career in the armed forces.

The motto of the NCC, "Unity and discipline," serves as a guiding principle for cadets in their contribution to Nation-building. We are indeed fortunate to identify as free citizens within a vast nation, encompassing a diverse population of various castes, creeds, sects, religions, and beliefs. Despite these differences and notable distinctions, India remains a testament to "unity in diversity," showcasing its resilience and inclusivity.

(b) A Teacher as NCC Officer

The teacher of institution is only entitled to become Associate NCC Officer for local NCC platoon/unit after basic training provide by NCC organization as per rule and regulation. ANO is basically a teacher which is an important trained person decorates NCC in the intuition and makes bridge between students and NCC battalion in different areas of state. There are two training centers as OTA Kamptee for male teachers and OTA Gwalior for female teachers. These two training centers train the school and college teachers selected by the combine efforts of NCC authority and head of institution. After basic Course of ninety days in the training center, the participant get commission and entitled to wear the uniform of NCC officer Ranked as lieutenant. After get this Rank, although the teacher remains a teacher but he enjoys some facilities as an Officer of armed forces. Beside this, teachers have to enhance their carrier advancement because of the in charge officer of this extension programme.

(c) Cadets' Practices to National Building

The primary activity of the NCC revolves around institutional training for cadets, designed to instill a profound sense of patriotism, discipline, and confidence. This training encompasses basic military subjects relevant to the Army, Navy or Air Force, aimed at familiarizing youth with a regimental lifestyle and fostering values such as discipline, duty, personal integrity, organization and neatness. Through these objectives, the NCC endeavors to cultivate a resilient and audacious future generation, poised to contribute positively to society and the nation.

Participation in various camps, including the Army Attachment Camp, Thal Sena Camp, Combined Annual Training Camp, and Republic Day Camp, enables cadets to live, dine, and train together, facilitating exposure to the customs, traditions, and temperaments of their peers. This experience nurtures a spirit of unity, solidarity, and collaboration.

National Integration Camps (NIC) are organized throughout the country with the aim of instilling in cadets the understanding that the honor, welfare, and security of the nation take precedence over individual interests. The ethos of the NCC emphasizes on placing the nation and its citizens above personal welfare at all times.

Moreover, NCC cadets are provided with numerous opportunities to engage in adventurous pursuits such as camping, trekking to mountains, mountaineering, scuba diving, rafting, gliding, para jumping, flying, hiking, rock climbing, micro-light flying, slithering and cycle/motorcycle expeditions. These adventurous endeavors emphasize courage and confidence, nurturing a strong sense of duty towards the nation.

Within the realm of social activities aimed at community development, NCC cadets actively participate in various initiatives such as adult education programs, blood donation drives, flood relief operations, environmental conservation efforts, traffic control, and other rescue and relief operations. Additionally, a significant number of cadets annually engage in campaigns against dowry and pledge for eye donation. The objective behind organizing these activities is to cultivate awareness and sensitivity among young individuals towards the needs and challenges faced by their fellow countrymen, thereby contributing to societal development, which is a crucial aspect of nation-building.

Furthermore, an integral component of NCC training is the Youth Exchange Program. Recognizing the importance of fostering international understanding and awareness, the NCC facilitates youth exchange programs with organizations from ten countries including Australia, Bangladesh, Bhutan, Canada, Maldives, Nepal, Singapore, Sri Lanka, and the United Kingdom. This

exchange program entails mutual visits by cadets for duration of three months, during which they engage in community development projects and conduct studies on the history, culture, and socio-economic conditions of the participating countries. These Youth Exchange Programs provide the youth of our nation with a deeper understanding of the global landscape and equip them with the skills needed to become effective leaders in the future. Under the Overseas Deployment, some selected cadets from the SD (Navy) are attached to the Indian Navy for Training of 30-45 days, wherein they will practice in Naval Subjects, Seamanship Practical and attitudes to become travel friend for abroad nations on Goodwill Missions.

NCC cadets who attain 'B' and 'C' certificates are accorded preferential treatment in admissions to esteemed academic institutions offering education in various fields such as medicine, engineering, administration, teaching, and more. Upon completing their education, these cadets emerge as responsible individuals committed to serving society. 'C' certificate holders also enjoy reservations in the Armed Forces, and state Governments provide additional weightage in Government job opportunities. Consequently, conscientious and upright professionals such as doctors, administrators, engineers, teachers, and security personnel contribute significantly to the process of nation-building.

Raj Kumar & others (2018) studied about NCC cadets and non NCC students for leadership potential and emphasized that the NCC operates as a dynamic and adaptable institution, committed to ongoing learning and development. They emphasized the importance of certain fundamental principles that they strive to imbue within all levels of the organization. These principles include valuing diversity in religion, language, culture, ethnicity, lifestyle, and habitat, with the aim of fostering national unity and social cohesion. Additionally, they underscored the significance of being attuned to the needs of economically disadvantaged individuals and recognizing the importance of virtues such as truthfulness, honesty, self-sacrifice, hard work and perseverance.

Prime Minister of India, Shri Narendra Modi (2024) expresses happiness over improvement in performance of Indian Universities in QS World University Ranking and said that over the last decade, we have worked on fruitful changes in the education set up and the result is shown in the QS World University Rankings. He gave hearty congratulations to the teaching faculties, students and institutions' authorities for their hard work and dedication towards achievement of objectives. He emphasized that we want to do work even more to highlight research and innovation in this field of education.

Conclusion

The training of the NCC is so planned and integrated with the educational and social requirements of the nation and society. The youngsters who are great to take part hold big potential of emerging as open minded, self-confident and progressive individuals. As Churchill once remarked, "I love to learn but I hate to be taught." Recognizing that education extends beyond academic pursuits, the NCC effectively bridges the gap between learning and personal growth through its co-curricular activities, fostering a sense of discovery and self-improvement without the traditional constraints of teaching. The NCC is dedicated to promoting core values such as humanism, patriotism, and selfless service, thereby contributing to the process of nation-building through its multifaceted activities. Recognizing its vital role, both the State and Central Governments should offer increased incentives to the NCC to enhance its popularity and usefulness in serving the nation. Many former cadets of NCC are today designated at senior positions in all Govt. services, social services, NGOs, environment, Politics, health services, teaching services and the corporate world. Therefore, the contribution of NCC for the socialization of the youth is highlighted all over the country.

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